

Numerical Modeling of the Lower Corona during the Total Solar Eclipse of 2010 July 11

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ABSTRACT

We perform and analyze the results of a global magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) simulation of the lower solar corona and compare with observations taken during the total solar eclipse that occurred on 2010 July 11. Total eclipses serve as the primary sources to study the lower corona, and the thermodynamics of the eclipse of July 11 was extensively studied by *Habbal et al, 2011*, which included an in-depth analysis of multi-wavelength coronal observations. In this study, we use the three dimensional Alfvén Wave Solar Model (AWSoM), which addresses the coronal heating and solar wind acceleration with low frequency Alfvén wave turbulence, to simulate solar wind properties, broadband white light and multi-wavelength extreme ultraviolet images and compare with the observations from *SOHO/LASCO C2* coronagraph, *STEREO/EUVI* and the *Solar Dynamics Observatory/AIA* instruments, in addition to performing comparisons of 1 AU solar wind properties with observations from *STEREO A/B* and the *OMNIWeb* dataset. We also simulate white light images with an occultation of 1 radius of Sun (R_{\odot}) resembling an eclipse image, for comparison with white-light total eclipse images. We find good agreement of the morphology of the lower corona with both white light and EUV images. The model is sparsely able to capture the dynamic structures observed during the eclipse.

Keywords: magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) — Eclipses — methods : numerical — WL Images — solar wind — Sun : corona

NUMERICAL MODELING OF THE LOWER CORONA DURING THE TOTAL SOLAR ECLIPSE OF 2010 JULY 11

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ABSTRACT

We perform and analyze the results of a global magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) simulation of the lower solar corona and compare with observations taken during the total solar eclipse that occurred on 2010 July 11. Total eclipses serve as the primary sources to study the lower corona, and the thermodynamics of the eclipse of July 11 was extensively studied by [Habbal et al. \(2011\)](#), which included an in-depth analysis of multi-wavelength coronal observations. In this study, we use the three dimensional Alfvén Wave Solar Model (AWSoM), which addresses the coronal heating and solar wind acceleration with low frequency Alfvén wave turbulence, to simulate solar wind properties, broadband white light and multi-wavelength extreme ultraviolet images and compare with the observations from *SOHO/LASCO C2* coronagraph, *STEREO/EUVI* and the *Solar Dynamics Observatory/AIA* instruments, in addition to performing comparisons of 1 AU solar wind properties with observations from *STEREO A/B* and the *OMNIWeb* dataset. We also simulate white light images with an occultation of 1 radius of Sun (R_{\odot}) resembling an eclipse image, for comparison with white-light total eclipse images. We find good agreement of the morphology of the lower corona with both white light and EUV images. The model is sparsely able to capture the dynamic structures observed during the eclipse.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The solar corona is an extension of the Sun's atmosphere, made of ionized plasma that is organized by the solar magnetic field into distinct structures. Away from the Sun, radial acceleration of this coronal plasma eventually forms the solar wind, which extends into interplanetary space. Understanding the process dominating the ambient solar corona and solar wind is a crucial step in the study and prediction of space weather. Over the past few decades, considerable progress has been made in the understanding and modeling of the solar atmosphere due to the increased availability of observational data and the development of analytical tools and numerical models to simulate the solar corona. Important in the further progress of these models is a better understanding of the problem of coronal heating and solar wind acceleration. Observations from *Hinode* have shown the larger extent of wave energetics present in the solar corona than previously believed, propagating away from the Sun, to heat the corona and maintain the temperatures at 1 MK (De Pontieu et al. 2007), prompting several attempts to develop 3D solar coronal (SC) and inner heliospheric (IH) models based on Alfvén wave turbulence, and check if such a theoretical model reproduces emission features seen in extreme ultraviolet (EUV) and white light images. Solar wind modeling has always been an active area of research dating back to the late 1960s. The inclusion of Alfvén wave turbulence in the solar wind dates back to the pioneering work of Coleman (1968), who concluded that turbulence is important in the solar wind near 1 AU. Earliest inclusion of Alfvén wave turbulence was conducted in Belcher & Davis (1971) and Alazraki & Couturier (1971) and have thereafter been a cornerstone in coronal modeling, often including various other properties such as wave reflection and mode conversion from Alfvén to slow waves (Matsumoto & Suzuki 2012), accounting for turbulent cascades and/or counter-propagating waves explaining the incompressible cascade and the coronal heating (Velli et al. 1989). Several other attempts (Leer & Axford 1972; Isenberg 1984; Fichtner & Fahr 1991; Vásquez et al. 2003; Li et al. 2004; Chandran et al. 2011) have also taken into consideration the importance of proton temperature anisotropy which is observed frequently through *in-situ* data.

In recent years, the solar wind modeling efforts in the Space Weather Modeling Framework (SWMF, Tóth et al. 2012) have been focused around the development and validation of the Alfvén Wave Solar Model (AWSoM, van der Holst et al. 2014; Meng et al. 2015). AWSoM has been developed from previous works (van der Holst et al. 2010; Jin et al. 2012; Sokolov et al. 2013; Oran et al. 2013), which began with a two-temperature Alfvén wave-driven solar model. The physics incorporated into the model allows for the generation of realistic LOS images and 1 AU solar wind predictions.

Initial validation of the corona was conducted in the study by van der Holst et al. (2014) which introduced the coronal heating model, validating it against multi-wavelength extreme ultraviolet (EUV) images from *STEREO A/B* and *AIA* instrument, while validation for 1AU observations was carried out in Meng et al. (2015) for two Carrington Rotations, which also described the anisotropic extension to the model. The present AWSoM incorporates physically based wave reflection, energy partition, collisionless heat conduction and temperature anisotropy. More details of the model has been contained in Section 2.

In this study, the simulation of the lower corona has been conducted to validate AWSoM's theoretical approach in solving for the coronal heating and solar wind acceleration. The lower or inner corona starting from the solar surface out to heliocentric distances of 5 - 10 solar radii (R_{\odot}), is attributed to be the region where the imprint of the physical processes responsible for heating the coronal plasma and accelerating the solar wind is the most conspicuous. Observations of the solar corona in general have been made possible with the use of both space and ground based observatories, which have provided us with both qualitative and quantitative data for comparisons. However, direct observations of the lower corona is enormously difficult with such instruments and can only be studied during total eclipses. The optical emission of the solar corona is several orders of magnitude lesser than the photosphere (surface) of the sun, and therefore can only be observed when the surface of the sun is occulted. Such opportunities are provided during total solar eclipses and these instances have been used to study the various properties of the plasma surrounding the sun; Lyot's invention of the coronagraph (Lyot 1932) significantly improved the observational conditions of the sun in polarized and unpolarized light within some of the coronal forbidden lines (Newkirk et al. 1970). However, imaging and spectroscopy with a coronagraph remains limited to distances above $1.05 R_{\odot}$ due to diffraction at the edge of the occulter, and below $1.5 R_{\odot}$ due to the limited reduction of sky brightness down to the levels experienced during totality beyond that distance. In addition, albeit the massive diagnostic capabilities provided by the extreme ultraviolet (EUV) wavelength ranges have provided opportunities to image the corona on both the disk and limb thereby establishing sources of the intricate structures, even these capabilities are limited to distances below $1.5 R_{\odot}$ due to the collisional dominance of the emissions decreasing with distance as the square of the density. Owing to such reasons, total solar eclipses continue to serve as the primary source of observational data to study the lower corona.

In this study, we describe the global simulation of a total eclipse event that took place on July 11, 2010 and was

reported with multi-wavelength coronal images by [Habbal et al. \(2011\)](#). Habbal and collaborators have been studying the lower corona using total solar eclipses ([Habbal et al. 2007a, 2007b, 2010a, 2010b](#)), and successfully showed the diagnostic capabilities of the coronal forbidden lines in the visible wavelength. In this work, however, we have considered broadband white light images of the eclipse in addition to extreme ultra-violet (EUV) images from satellites. The Large Angle Spectrometric Coronagraph (*LASCO*) C2 and C3 are a set of white light wide-angle coronagraphs aboard the *Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO)* spacecraft which generate white light images above different solar radii, provide unique opportunities to study the structure of the solar corona in real time. But, as discussed earlier, the coronagraphs are limited to viewing above 2.3 solar radii (C2) and 3.7 solar radii (C3) from the center of the Sun in their observations. This paper describes the first simulation of a total eclipse and presents resulting multi-wavelength EUV and broadband white light images of the Sun and compares them with observational data. In Section 2, we present details about the numerical methodology used and its implementation for the present case. In Section 3, we have described the event and the observations as studied by ([Habbal et al. 2011](#)) in their initial paper. In Section 4, the performance of the model for the given case is compared using EUV images with observations along with 1 AU comparisons for solar acceleration and magnetic field, and we conclude in Section 5.

2. THE ALFVÉN WAVE SOLAR MODEL

We use the Alfvén Wave Solar Model presented in the works by [van der Holst et al. \(2014\)](#) and [Meng et al. \(2015\)](#) for the simulation of the lower corona. The solar model constitutes two major modules: the solar corona (SC) and the inner heliosphere (IH). In this work, the two-temperature MHD equations have been solved for the ions and electrons with the incorporation of the Alfvén wave turbulence. Brief details of the governing equations have been presented in Section 2.1, while the numerical implementation has been discussed in Section 2.2.

2.1. Governing Physics

The governing equations for the AWSoM are

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(\rho \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \left(\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u} - \frac{\mathbf{B} \mathbf{B}}{\mu_0} \right) \\ + \nabla \cdot \left(P_i + P_e + \frac{\mathbf{B}^2}{2\mu_0} + P_A \right) = -\rho \frac{GM_\odot}{r^3} \mathbf{r}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} - \nabla \times (\mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B}) = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{P_i}{\gamma-1} + \frac{\rho u^2}{2} + \frac{\mathbf{B}^2}{2\mu_0} \right) \\ + \nabla \cdot \left[\left(\frac{\rho u^2}{2} + \frac{\gamma P_i}{\gamma-1} + \frac{\mathbf{B}^2}{\mu_0} \right) \mathbf{u} - \frac{\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{B})}{\mu_0} \right] = \\ -(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla)(P_e + P_A) + \frac{N_i k_B}{\tau_{ei}} (T_e - T_i) + Q_i - \rho \frac{GM_\odot}{r^3} \mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{u}, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{P_e}{\gamma-1} \right) + \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{P_e}{\gamma-1} \mathbf{u} \right) + P_e \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = \\ -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_e + \frac{N_i k_B}{\tau_{ei}} (T_i - T_e) - Q_{rad} + Q_e, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where ρ and \mathbf{u} are the mass density and velocity, \mathbf{B} is the magnetic field, G is the gravitational constant, M_\odot is the solar mass, \mathbf{r} is the position vector relative to the center of the Sun, with $r = |\mathbf{r}|$, μ_0 is the permeability of vacuum. Equations 1 and 2 describe the mass conservation and momentum conservation equations. Equation 3 describes the induction equation. The initial conditions should satisfy $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$. The Alfvén wave pressure, P_A , provides the additional solar wind acceleration. The energy conservation solves for the isotropic ion pressure P_i and electron pressure P_e separately, by using Equations 4 and 5, in which $T_{e,i}$ are the electron and ion temperatures, $N_{e,i}$ are the electron and ion number densities, and k_B is the Boltzmann constant. Anisotropy has not been studied in the following study. To supplement the above equations, more physics has been included from previous studies. The optically radiative energy loss term Q_{rad} in the lower corona has been defined as

$$Q_{rad} = N_e N_h \Lambda(T_e) \quad (6)$$

where N_h is the hydrogen number density and $\Lambda(T_e)$ is the radiative cooling curve taken from the CHIANTI version 7.1 database ([Landi et al. 2013](#)). The Coulomb collisional energy change between the ions and electrons depends on the relaxation time τ_{ei} . The electron heat flux \mathbf{q}_e has been split into two contributions. The collisional formulation of [Spitzer \(1962\)](#) denoted as $\mathbf{q}_{e,S}$ along with the collisionless heat flux of [Hollweg \(1978\)](#) denoted as $\mathbf{q}_{e,H}$ have been incorporated as follows:

$$\mathbf{q}_e = f_s \mathbf{q}_{e,S} + (1 - f_s) \mathbf{q}_{e,H} \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{q}_{e,S} = -\kappa_e T_e^{5/2} \mathbf{b} \mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla T_e \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{q}_{e,H} = \frac{3}{2} \alpha p_e \mathbf{u} \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{B}/B$, $\alpha = 1.05$, $\kappa_e \approx 9.2 \times 10^{-12} \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-7/2}$ and f_s is *Spitzer* heat flux fraction defined as a function of r . The Alfvén wave pressure and total wave dissipation is solved using the propagation, reflection and dissipation of the wave

energy densities, w_{\pm} (+ sign is for waves propagating in the direction parallel to \mathbf{B} , while the $-$ sign is for waves propagating antiparallel to \mathbf{B}). The time evolution of w_{\pm} can be described as

$$\frac{\partial w_{\pm}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot [(\mathbf{u} \pm \mathbf{V}_A)w_{\pm}] + \frac{w_{\pm}}{2} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) = \mp \mathcal{R} \sqrt{w_{-}w_{+}} - \Gamma_{\pm} w_{\pm} \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{V}_A = \mathbf{B}/\sqrt{\mu_0 \rho}$ is the Alfvén speed, Γ_{\pm} is the wave dissipation rate and \mathcal{R} is the signed reflection rate. The theoretical explanation and numerical implementation of the above plasma properties have been discussed in detail in [van der Holst et al. \(2014\)](#).

2.2. Model Implementation

The global simulation is performed with two individual models, the solar corona (SC) and the inner heliosphere (IH), each of which is based on the original Block-Adaptive-Tree-Solarwind-Roe-Upwind-Scheme (BATS-R-US; [Powell et al. 1999](#)). These models are three of a dozen components that can be run under the Space Weather Modeling Framework ([Tóth et al. 2012](#)).

The SC model is a data-driven model which is provided with an initial boundary condition of the magnetic field by an MDI synoptic magnetogram, while the initial magnetic field configuration is calculated by the Potential Field Source Surface (PFSS) model, using a finite difference method (FDIPS) described in [Tóth et al. \(2011\)](#). The model uses a 3D stretched spherical grid with the radial coordinates ranging from $1 R_{\odot}$ to $24 R_{\odot}$, with radial resolution varying from about $0.001 R_{\odot}$ near the surface of the Sun to about $1 R_{\odot}$ further away from the Sun. The angular cell size is about 1.4° inside $1.7 R_{\odot}$ and 2.8° outside, in both meridional and azimuthal directions. The transition region is artificially broadened by fixing the temperature and density in the upper chromosphere at $50,000K$ and $2 \times 10^{17} m^{-3}$ respectively. At the base of the atmosphere, the temperature is kept constant while the density is let to exponentially decrease to a level where the radiative losses are sufficiently low in order to increase the temperature monotonically with height. The meteoric rise of the temperature above this height forms the transition region. For more detail, please refer to [Lionello et al. \(2009\)](#) and [Sokolov et al. \(2013\)](#). The IH component has a square box as its computational domain surrounding the spherical SC domain. The box extends from -250 to $250 R_{\odot}$ along the Cartesian coordinates in X , Y and Z directions. The grid is block decomposed using the block-adaptive tree library ([Tóth et al. 2012](#)). The grid blocks consist of $6 \times 4 \times 4$ mesh cells in the SC component, while consisting of $4 \times 4 \times 4$ mesh cells in the IH component. For the generation of finer images, grid blocks containing $6 \times 6 \times 6$ mesh cells were used in the SC component.

3. EVENT DESCRIPTION & ECLIPSE OBSERVATIONS

[Habbal et al. \(2011\)](#) made the eclipse observations of 2010 July 11 from the atoll of Tatakoto in French Polynesia at S $17^{\circ}20'39''.3$, W $138^{\circ}27'3''.1$. Totality, or second contact, C_2 , occurred at 18:45:36 UT, and third contact, C_3 , occurred at 18:50:05 UT, with a total duration of 4 minutes 29s. The Sun was at an altitude of 35.5° above the horizon at C_2 . The authors described the observing conditions as not perfect, with sporadic clouds passing in front of the eclipsed Sun throughout the duration of totality. They also report the eruption of two large prominences and the passage of their affiliated coronal mass ejections (CMEs) through the corona around 4 hours earlier to the event, leaving behind detectable imprint in the coronal structures.

Figure 1. Broadband white light image of the corona. The brightest features appearing in white, have been labeled further in the second diagram for further detail. Several small scale loops can be observed in the north-eastern and south-western sides of the corona. The south-eastern limb is dominated by the formation of the *Streak*. A large loop forms on the north-western limb.

Arch-like structures are visible near the limb of the Sun in almost all the regions except for the poles. These are a com-

Figure 2. The simulated solar wind properties along the *STEREO A/B* trajectories compared with the observations from *STEREO-A/B* for CR2098. Here U_r stands for radial flow velocity, N_p stands for number density and B is the magnitude of the magnetic field.

plex of small, seemingly intertwined, loop-like structures which form away from the poles. The smallest arches are about $1.1 R_\odot$ in height. Overlying these smaller loops is an intricate and larger set of loops reaching heights of approximately $1.23 R_\odot$, with the most evident one appearing in the north-eastern side. Beyond $1.2 R_\odot$, the corona's brightness becomes extremely low to observe detailed structures without further image processing. Habbal et al. (2011), using their NRGF and ACHF filter (Morgan et al. 2006; Druckmüller et al. 2006; Druckmüller 2009; Morgan et al. 2009) observe a complex set of converging and diverging open field lines, containing streamer-like structures. They also observe ripples and wave-like structures at the boundary of a streamer in the south-west.

The effect of the coronal mass ejection is evident from the observation of the features labeled *Streak* and *Cone* in Figure 1(a). A third feature appearing in the western side (labeled *Hook* in Habbal et al. 2011, due to its twisted structure) is not visible in Figure 1, and therefore has not been discussed in much detail than is necessary. The origin of these structures were studied in detail by Habbal and collaborators using EUV emissions and white light coronagraph observations from LASCO C2 images, which included the careful comparison of spectral line images for various wavelengths in visible and EUV wavelength ranges, concluding the emergence of these structures due to eruptive prominences and CMEs. The *Streak* and the *Cone* form a sharp C-shaped curve that intercepts the solar disk at a position angle of 230° . The emergence of streamer-like structures in the south-western region is evidently clear in the C2 images considered in the present

Figure 3. The simulated solar wind properties along the terrestrial orbit compared with the observations from *OMNIWeb* data set for CR2098. Here U_r stands for radial flow velocity, N_p stands for number density and B is the magnitude of the magnetic field.

study as well. A general yet interesting observation would be the fact that the generation of these structures are in the lower corona at a height of about $1-3 R_\odot$, a region which is not imaged by any other instrument presently.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

Figure 4. Comparisons between synthesized and observational EUV images of the steady-state solar wind model. The observation time is 2011 July 10, $\sim 18:45:00$ UT. The columns are from left to right for 171Å, 195Å and 284Å. Top panels: Synthesized EUV images of the model for the *STEREO-A* trajectory. Panels in second row: Observational images from *STEREO A/EUVI* for the respective wavelengths. Panels in third row: Synthesized EUV images of the model for the *STEREO-B* trajectory. Bottom Panels: Observational images from *STEREO B/EUVI* for the respective wavelengths.

Figure 5. Comparisons between synthesized and observational EUV images of the steady-state solar wind model (contd.). The observation time is 2011 July 10, $\sim 18:45:00$ UT. Top panels (from left to right): Synthesized EUV images for 94\AA , 171\AA and 193\AA of the model for the *SDO* trajectory. Panels in second row: Observational images from *SDO/AIA* imager for respective wavelengths. Third Panel: Synthesized EUV images for 131\AA , 211\AA and 335\AA of the model for the *SDO* trajectory. Bottom Panels: Observational images from *SDO/AIA* imager for respective wavelengths.

To simulate the above event at the given time, the radial magnetic field component in the inner boundary (located at the upper chromosphere) was specified by the synoptic map CR2098 obtained from the *SOHO*/Michelson Doppler Imager (MDI) with interpolated polar field data. We use FDIPS to generate an initial condition for the magnetic field and the boundary condition values for the radial magnetic field component.

4.1. Solar Wind Properties Comparisons at 1 AU

As an initial validation of the model for the given Carrington Rotation, we compare the simulated solar wind properties at 1 AU to satellite observations. Figure 2 shows the comparison of the simulations with the *STEREO A/B* satellites which revolve around the Sun in counter directions to each other. The *STEREO-A* satellite orbits a little closer to the Sun than *STEREO-B*. The simulated properties match well with

Figure 6. LASCO C2 Images: Comparisons between observed (left) and simulated (right) broadband white light images of the steady-state solar wind with normalized brightness intensity. The observation time is 2011 July 10, \sim 18:36:00 UT.

those observed. AWSoM is able to model the solar wind speed quite accurately, while being able to sparsely follow a similar trend as that of the number density and magnetic field B . The model underestimates the density peaks in the data probably from ICMEs as observed by *STEREO-A* while overestimating the quiet solar time. The opposite happens for *STEREO-B*, where the model slightly overestimates the peak formed due to an ICME on June 22, 2010 albeit being able to predict the event occurrence accurately. It neither overestimates nor underestimates the flow velocity and the magnetic field magnitude. It is not able to do a significant job in predicting the temperature of the solar wind.

The model has also been validated with data sets from the OMNIWeb consisting of observations from different satellites since 1963 (Papitashvili et al. 2014). Like the previous comparisons, AWSoM predicts the solar wind velocity accurately. It has a time delay of several hours in predicting the peaks in the magnetic field magnitude on and around June 27 2010, but neither over predicts nor under predicts the magnitude. It is accurately able to predict the magnitude change and location of a probable ICME on the same day. It under predicts the temperature of ions, albeit following a close trend similar to the observations.

4.2. EUV Comparisons

Observations from the 1 AU comparisons served as a basis for further detailed comparisons of the coronal structures using extreme ultra-violet (EUV) images. From the density and electron temperature distributions, calculated by AWSoM, EUV images can be synthesized to compare with observed data. The simulated density, temperature, and instrumental response functions constructed from CHIANTI 7.1 atomic database (Landi et al. 2013) are used to synthesize EUV images which are then compared with observed EUV images. EUV images also shed light into the near limb structures in

the corona and therefore is of immense importance to the present study as we are interested in looking at the presence of defining structures from AWSoM that might be comparable to the observations post CME.

To better resolve the details in the synthesized LOS images, the latitudinal and longitudinal resolution has been increased by using adaptive mesh refinement grid size of $6 \times 6 \times 6$ and solved for by using a spatially 5th order MP5 limiter. In Figure 4, emission images in the three coronal bandpasses for Fe emission lines at 171, 195 and 284Å were computed for the *STEREO A/B* trajectory and compared with observations from the *STEREO/EUVI* emission images (Howard et al. 2008). AWSoM is able to model the general configurations of the near coronal structures. The model predicts larger coronal holes than the observed images. The active regions are not distinctly captured but identifiable. The coronal structures identifiable from the *STEREO A/B* comparisons show a good agreement with observations. Although the larger structures visible in the broadband white light are not distinctly identifiable in the observations as well as the simulations, the comparisons for the wavelengths 195Å and 284Å provide fruitful results as to the intensity of the coronal density on the limbs, when compared with the observations.

Comparisons have also been conducted with EUV images from the Solar Dynamics Observatory/AIA imager (Lemen et al. 2012). In Figure 5, emission images in six different coronal bandpasses were computed and compared with SDO/AIA images. While several of the images (particularly 94Å and 131 Å cases) show presence of large coronal holes, these are not corroborated with observations. As in the previous case, the location of the active regions are sparsely identifiable in the simulations. The 171Å and 193Å simulation cases show good agreement with its observed counterparts.

Figure 7. Eclipse Images: Comparisons between observed (left) and simulated (right) white light images of the steady-state solar wind with normalized brightness. Top Panel: Grayscale comparisons of the coronal structure for similar normalized intensities. Bottom Panel: Contour comparisons of the interior structures for both cases for similar normalized intensities. The observation time is 2011 July 10, 18:45:36 (Totality, C₂).

As pointed out in Habbal et al. (2011), EUV images serve as a good check to understand the coronal dynamics, but have excessively low brightness beyond $1.5 R_{\odot}$, deeming them useless to compare coronal structures visible during eclipses. We, therefore, look at simulations of broadband white light images,

4.3. Broadband White Light Comparisons

In this study, broadband white light comparisons were conducted using two sources of observations: *SOHO/LASCO* C2 Coronagraph images and the total eclipse images from Habbal et al. (2011). Generation of the simulated images was construed through the use of Thomson Scattering. The light of the corona typically consists of three parts: a) The emission lines; they have a total intensity of about half a percent of the integrated light, b) The major part of the sunlight that is scattered by the free electrons of the corona, and c) The outer general haze around the Sun. For the generation of white light images, the second and major part of the sunlight is most important. This part has two major

components based on how each of them are produced - the *K* and *F* corona. The *Kontinuerlich*, or *K*-corona arises from the Thomson scattering of light by free electrons in the corona, while the Fraunhofer or *F* corona refers to the "spurious" corona arising from scattering due to interplanetary dust. There are significant differences between these two components. For instance, the *F* corona is polarized within $5-6 R_{\odot}$, while the *K* corona is polarized. The *K* corona falls off more rapidly with distance and is more dominant close to the Sun. The *F* corona is largely unaffected by dynamic event such as CMEs (Billings 1966). van de Hulst (1950) in his classical paper presented a novel inversion method of deriving the electron density of the solar corona from eclipse measurements in polarized white light. The inversion of the brightness observations to obtain the electron density is critically dependent on the removal of the *F* corona contribution to the total brightness (Hayes et al. 2001). Since there is no interplanetary dust in AWSoM's simulated environment, calculation of the *K* coronal electron density is conducted simply through Thomson scattering. The Thomson-scattered

light of the synthetic images are numerically integrated along a LOS using an appropriate scattering function (Manchester et al. 2008). The observational images, C2 for instance, have to undergo removal of the F coronal component. Complete removal of the F corona from LASCO C2 images is conducted using a series of steps described in Hayes et al. (2001) and Saito et al. (1977) and explained together as a compiled process in Fainshtein (2009).

Figure 6 presents the LASCO C2 comparisons with the observed image on the left, and the simulated image on the right. The simulated image exhibits coronal properties typically seen in solar minimum conditions, with the presence of polar plumes and equatorial streamer (Billings 1966), and has a general agreement with the observed C2 image. It is, however, not that successful in resolving the two distinct streamers on the west, as is clearly visible in the observations. It also appears to have more coronal density around the Sun than is seen in observations. This, however, may also be attributed to the reduction in brightness in C2 observations caused due to the inaccuracy of K and F corona separation which dwindles with distance, as explained in Fainshtein (2009). In Figure 7, the comparison of the eclipse is made at $1 R_{\odot}$ with the total solar eclipse images presented in Habbal et al. (2011). For this case, we present a grayscale image and a contour image to better understand the coronal structure around the Sun. As can be evidently studied, while there are sharp, bright structures visible in the observed images, the simulated image shows equatorial streamers and is not clearly able to model the prominences on the surface or the dynamic structures like the *Cone* and *Streak* (See Section 3).

In general, the simulated broadband white light images show satisfactory agreement with the typical structure of the corona during a solar minimum condition. However, they also help state the case for a non-steady state time-dependent run of AWSoM to understand and help generate the various structures explained in Section 3. A general tilt towards the eastern side has been observed in the simulated images, which is probably due to numerical error in the density mapping.

5. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

We have performed a detailed analysis of a 3D MHD steady-state simulation of an eclipse event that was observed on July 11 2010, in order to study the physics of the lower corona. The simulation was carried out using the solar corona (SC) and inner heliosphere (IH) modules of the Alfvén Wave Solar Model (AWSoM), which is itself a part of the larger Space Weather Modeling Framework (SWMF). We have created synthetic images of the Sun on the day

of the event in the extreme ultra-violet (EUV) and broadband white light range of wavelengths and made qualitative comparisons of the white light images with those made by LASCO C2 coronagraph and the eclipse images captured and presented by Habbal et al. (2011). The EUV images have been compared with data from the *STEREO/EUVI* and *SDO/AIA* instruments. The simulation closely resembles the general structure and physics of the lower coronal observations, in both morphology and normalized magnitude of the Thomson-scattered light for both C2 and eclipse cases. The comparisons of the synthesized EUV images with those observed also produce a general agreement of the solar surface and limbs, and the lower corona to a height below $1.5 R_{\odot}$. Furthermore, the simulations have also been compared quantitatively with the *OMNIWeb* data sets and *STEREO A/B* solar wind data at a distance of 1 AU from the Sun for context, and are in close agreement.

The simulation is one of the first of its kind, and was successful in identifying several of the key factors observed by both the space-based and ground-based instruments. It is, however, unsuccessful in obtaining the detailed structures of the eclipse as described in Section 3. A larger aspect of this problem can be significantly improved by using a time-dependent simulation of the same event. As pointed out with detailed analysis of the spectral line images by Habbal et al. (2011), the generation of several of the coronal structures have been due to the generation of transient structures, such as the CME occurrence a couple hours before the eclipse observation or the generation of the *Hook* which, as they have explained, is a result of a prominence eruption.

We conclude by noting that the interestingly peculiar behaviour of the lower corona defines several aspects in the outer and middle corona at the height of greater than $2 R_{\odot}$. As can be clearly evident from both the observations and the simulations, the structures formed at the lower corona define the larger structures like streamers and helmets, and it is essential to consider these as transient events. As was shown through this study, consideration of a steady-state eclipse event may prove futile without the serious consideration of the state of the Sun before and after the event along with the valid inclusion of time-difference schemes coupled with steady-state schemes.

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